

HAPPINESS AS THE PREDICTOR OF LIFE SATISFACTION: JOB SATISFACTION AS THEIR MEDIATOR

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Abstract

Happiness is the positive emotion of joy, satisfaction, and gladness. Job satisfaction is one's attitude towards one's job or its components expressed in hedonic liking or disliking. Life satisfaction is the extent of satisfaction with life. Happiness in an employee's life contributes to their life satisfaction but is job satisfaction a reason for this relationship? The question inspired this study among 325 employees ($M_{age}=35.42$, $SD_{age}=9.34$) of Nepal. Using a mediation model, the answer has been sought. A survey was prepared using scales to measure happiness, life satisfaction and job satisfaction. The results showed that job satisfaction partially mediated the relationship between happiness and life satisfaction, with direct effect=.40, indirect effect=.14, excluding 0 in bootstrap 95% CI. So, the conclusion is that employee or related organization should try to enhance employees' happiness and job satisfaction because happier employees have more life satisfaction but this satisfaction is caused because of job satisfaction.

Keywords: work-life balance, spillover effect, job satisfaction, life satisfaction, organizational behavior

INTRODUCTION

Happiness is a positive emotion. Life and job satisfaction can be considered attitude. However, they all can be considered elements of subjective well-being despite being different psychological constructs. Well being consists of feeling good and being able to function well (Ruggeri et al., 2020).

Happiness

Happiness is the emotion of joy and gladness. It also reflects satisfaction and well-being (VandenBos, 2015). Happiness includes positive emotions ranging from low intensity like tranquility to high intensity like euphoria (Lyubomirsky & Kurtz, 2008). There are individual differences in the experience of happiness but it is related to strong social support, nurturance of the relationships, involvement in prosocial behaviors, expression of gratitude, meaningfulness of life, and commitment to goals. Happy people are optimistic realistically. They are mindful and do the physical exercises. They have the resources to cope with stress in life. Happy people are distinctly different in their behavioral and cognitive strategies than non-happy people (Lyubomirsky, 2001).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the positive feelings one derives from one's job after evaluation of various aspects of the job (Adhikari, 2020). It is a job attitude. So, it gets reflected not only in emotions but also in

cognition and behaviors. The factors related to job such as skill variety, individual employee such as self-esteem, growth opportunities such as promotion, and social factors such as organizational justice affect job satisfaction. A study (Adhikari, 2018) had shown that salary increase was associated to a slight increase in job satisfaction. The consequences of job satisfaction are seen in performance, withdrawal behaviors such as absenteeism, and counterproductive behaviors such as theft (Levy, 2017). Additionally, the consequence may also be on life satisfaction, positive emotions, social growth in life, and subjective well-being. The age, skillfulness, experience, and job security are positive correlates of job satisfaction (Katuwal & Randhawa, 2007). So is additional income. More number of dependents decreases job satisfaction.

Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction is the degree to which a person finds their life meaningful and rich. It represents extent of quality or fullness of life (VandenBos, 2015). Various factors affect life satisfaction. For example, the intensity and quality of friendship affect life satisfaction (Amati et al., 2018). Social support at workplace may be crucial. Similarly, the factors, like the nature and intensity of social support, related to workplace may affect life satisfaction. Financial satisfaction is a strong predictor of life satisfaction in poorer countries (Ed Diener & Diener, 2009). Self-efficacy is a predictor of life satisfaction (Wright & Perrone, 2010). The

other sources of life satisfaction may be recreation, spending quality time with family, break from work for refreshment, and appreciation of nature (Sirgy et al., 2011). Entrepreneurs rate their life satisfaction higher than employees do (Larsson & Thulin, 2019). Religiosity that promotes social capital can also predict life satisfaction (Okulicz-Kozaryn, 2010).

Relationship between Happiness, Life Satisfaction and Job Satisfaction

Positive emotions predict life satisfaction (Cohn et al., 2009). Happy people become more satisfied because they feel better and because they develop resources to live well (Cohn et al., 2009). Three orientations to happiness: pleasure, meaning and engagement, each can predict life satisfaction (Peterson et al., 2005). Higher job satisfaction predicts higher life satisfaction contemporaneously and longitudinally (Erdogan et al., 2012; Unanue et al., 2017). A Japanese study (Piccolo et al., 2005) found significant correlations between happiness, life and job satisfaction, and concluded that judgement of happiness and job satisfaction in non-Western culture has dispositional source. A Chinese study (Lambert et al., 2018) also showed the positive and significant correlation of life and job satisfaction.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of mediation of job satisfaction in the relationship of happiness and life satisfaction

Job satisfaction can have spillover effect. For example, daily job satisfaction can enhance daily marital satisfaction and affect at home (Ilies et al., 2009). Spillover hypothesis is supported by many studies (Rain et al., 1991). This study falls in that line to test spillover effect, which forms its theoretical framework.

Significance of the Study

Currently, studies testing the mediational effect of job satisfaction in relationship of psychological and life-related variables is lacking. Work-life balance is a buzzword and its benefits are pointed out (e.g., Tamang, 2010) but the way to achieve may not have

been tested empirically. This study aims to test if the spillover effect applies in the Nepalese context. Specifically, this study tests the hypothesis that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between happiness and life satisfaction in employees. The related mediation model is depicted in figure 1.

METHODS

This study is quantitative and has a survey design.

Participants

A convenient sample of 325 employees was made with the help of eight research assistants. More than half (54.5%) participants were males and remaining participants were female. More than one-fourth of participants (26.1%) were teachers, 41.5% were in service (including civil service), 5.2% were engineers, 8.6% were related to chartered accountancy, and others were in other occupations like medicine, driving, and labor. The sample consisted of 86.8% Hindu, 12.3% Buddhist, and remaining others were from other religions. Among them, 36.6% identified themselves as Baun, 7.8% as Chhetri, 19.7% as Newar, 4.6% as Tamang and the others introduced themselves as Magar, Chaurasiya, Chepang, Dalit, Gurung, Limbu, Madhesi, Patwa, Hamal, Puri, Rai, Sherpa and Tharu. Some of them did not reveal their ethnicity. Two-thirds (66.8%) participants lived in nuclear families and the remaining had joint family. Among all, 150 participants worked in governmental telecom corporation.

Instruments

Subjective happiness scale (SHS) with four items was used to measure happiness. Each item can be rated in the scale of 1-7 with 1 meaning “not a very happy person” and 7 meaning “a very happy person”. The happier person scores more in this scale. Life satisfaction was measured by satisfaction with life scale (SWLS; Diener et al., 1985)). It has five items that can be rated in seven points (1-7). In it, 1 means “strongly disagree”, and 7 means “strongly agree”. The higher score in it means more life satisfaction. Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire (MSQ; University of Minnesota, 1977) short form was used to measure job satisfaction. It has 20 items. Each item related to various aspects of job can be rated from “very dissatisfied” to “very satisfied”. The higher score in it means more job satisfaction.

Procedure

The questionnaire was prepared including the Nepali translation of psychological tests and a test to elicit demographic information. Eight research assistants (RAs) went to field to collect data. Informed consent was taken from participants. They filled the questionnaire up; the RAs clarified the items participants found confusing. The collected data were then entered into Excel.

Data Analysis

The data were organized in Excel and imported into SPSS where PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2018) was used to carry out a mediation model (model no. 4) with 50000 bootstrap samples. The hierarchical regression analysis was carried out without mediator in the first step and with it in the second step.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the means, quartiles and standard deviations of the three variables considered for the study.

Table 1 Means, quartiles and standard deviations for three variables in the study

Variable	M	SD	Q1	Q2	Q3
Life satisfaction (SWLS score)	22.99	6.030	18.00	21.00	23.00
Happiness (SHS score)	20.14	4.288	67.00	74.00	79.50
Job Satisfaction (MSQ-short form score)	72.58	10.979	20.00	23.00	27.00

Table 2 shows that happiness, life satisfaction and job satisfaction are all correlated significantly. In other words, they can predict each other. Regression

analysis from PROCESS result showed that 7.54% variance is explained by happiness on the prediction of job satisfaction of the employees.

Table 2: Bivariate correlation between variables

	Happiness	Job satisfaction
Job satisfaction	.275**	
Life satisfaction	.388**	.452**

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 (a result of hierarchical linear regression analysis) shows that happiness alone (in step 1) accounts for 15.1% variance, $F(1, 323)=57.39$, $p<.001$ and job satisfaction (in step 2) accounts for

additional 12.9% variance, $F(1, 322)=57.69$, $p<.001$ in the significant prediction of life satisfaction. They both account for 28% variance in life satisfaction in total.

Table 3: Variance of hierarchical regression analysis

Model	R	R ²	SE	Change Statistics				
				ΔR^2	ΔF	df1	df2	Sig. ΔF
1	.388 ^a	.151	5.565	.151	57.390	1	323	.000
2	.529 ^b	.280	5.133	.129	57.690	1	322	.000

Note. ^a represents happiness as predictor; ^b represents happiness and job satisfaction as predictors for the dependent variable life satisfaction

Table 4 shows the unstandardized and standardized coefficients. Considering β values, it is significant in step 1 and still significant at step 2 with happiness. So, job satisfaction is seen to partially

mediate the relationship between happiness and life satisfaction. The regression weight for happiness-life satisfaction has dropped from .388 to .286 and still remains significant.

Table 4. Coefficients of hierarchical regression analysis

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	95% CI for B	
		B	SE	β			Lower	Upper
1	(Constant)	11.984	1.485		8.070	.000	9.062	14.905
	Happiness	.546	.072	.388	7.576	.000	.404	.688
2	(Constant)	.000	2.089		.000	1.000	-4.111	4.110
	Happiness	.402	.069	.286	5.812	.000	.266	.538
	Job satisfaction	.205	.027	.374	7.595	.000	.152	.258

PROCESS results showed that indirect effect was significant, $ab=.14$, 95% CI [.0630, .2458]. So was direct effect, $c=.40$, 95% CI [.2659, .5381]. The total

effect was also significant, $c'=.55$, 95% CI [.4044, .6881]. Hence, one-fourth (25.45%) effect came from the mediation.

DISCUSSION

The conclusion is that 25% of effect of happiness on life satisfaction among Nepalese employees comes from job satisfaction. There is a partial mediation effect seen from the models tested. The concept of spillover effect gains confidence in this study. The practical implication of this is that organizations can enhance employees’ happiness and job satisfaction to increase their life satisfaction or to improve work-life balance. A recent study also found a positive association between work-life balance and life satisfaction or other aspects of personal life (Schnettler et al., 2021).

may limit the generalizability of findings. Employees from all occupations have not been represented. The future research can check if other factors related to work such as individual work performance, job stress, and social support mediate the relationship between happiness and life-satisfaction. The models can be tested for relationship between other variables like personality traits and well-being. This study also shows the possibility of Organizational Behavior (OB) model (Robbins & Judge, 2022, p. 58) to test the mediational role of processes in the relationship between input and output factors. Similarly, the mediation model tested for this study can be done for each specific occupations in the future.

There are some limitations in this research. The sample was convenient and this sampling method

increase life satisfaction by building resilience. *Emotion*, 9(3), 361–368. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0015952>

REFERENCES

Adhikari, P. (2018). Are higher earning teachers of Kathmandu more satisfied in job? *XICJ*, 1(1), 46–50.

Adhikari, P. (2020). *Industrial & Organizational Psychology*. Taleju Prakashan.

Amati, V., Meggiolaro, S., Rivellini, G., & Zaccarin, S. (2018). Social relations and life satisfaction: The role of friends. *Genus*, 74(7). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41118-018-0032-z>

Cohn, M. A., Fredrickson, B. L., Brown, S. L., Mikels, J. A., & Conway, A. M. (2009). Happiness unpacked: Positive emotions

Diener, E, Emmons, R., Larsen, R., & Griffin, S. (1985). The satisfaction with life scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49(1), 71–75.

Diener, Ed, & Diener, M. (2009). Cross-cultural correlates of life satisfaction and self-esteem. In *Culture and well-being* (pp. 71–91). Springer.

Erdogan, B., Bauer, T. N., Truxillo, D. M., & Mansfield, L. R. (2012). Whistle while you work: A review of the life satisfaction literature. *Journal of Management*, 38(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206311429379>

- Hayes, A. F. (2018). *Introduction to Mediation, Moderation, and Conditional Process Analysis: A Regression-Based Approach* (2nd ed.). Guilford Press.
- Ilies, R., Wilson, K. S., & Wagner, D. T. (2009). The spillover of daily job satisfaction onto employees' family lives: The facilitating role of work-family integration. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(1), 87–102.
- Katuwal, S. B., & Randhawa, G. (2007). Some personal attributes in association with job satisfaction of industrial workers of nepal. *Paradigm*, 11(1), 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0971890720070104>
- Lambert, E. G., Jiang, S., Liu, J., Zhang, J., & Choi, E. (2018). A happy life: Exploring how job stress, job involvement, and job satisfaction are related to the life satisfaction of Chinese prison staff. *Psychiatry, Psychology and Law*, 25(4), 619–636.
- Larsson, J. P., & Thulin, P. (2019). Independent by necessity? The life satisfaction of necessity and opportunity entrepreneurs in 70 countries. *Small Business Economics*, 53(4), 921–934. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-018-0110-9>
- Levy, P. E. (2017). *Industrial/Organizational Psychology: Understanding the Workplace* (5th ed.). Worth Publishers.
- Lyubomirsky, S. (2001). Why are some people happier than others? The role of cognitive and motivational processes in well-being. *American Psychologist*, 56(3), 239.
- Lyubomirsky, S., & Kurtz, J. (2008). *Positively Happy: Routes to Sustainable Happiness A Six Week Course*.
- Okulicz-Kozaryn, A. (2010). Religiosity and life satisfaction across nations. *Mental Health, Religion & Culture*, 13(2), 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13674670903273801>
- Peterson, C., Park, N., & Seligman, M. E. P. (2005). Orientations to happiness and life satisfaction: The full life versus the empty life. *Journal of Happiness Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-004-1278-z>
- Piccolo, R. F., Judge, T. A., Takahashi, K., Watanabe, N., & Locke, E. A. (2005). Core self-evaluations in Japan: relative effects on job satisfaction, life satisfaction, and happiness. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(8), 965–984. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.358>
- Rain, J. S., Lane, I. M., & Steiner, D. D. (1991). A current look at the job satisfaction/life satisfaction relationship: Review and future considerations. *Human Relations*, 44(3), 287–307. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872679104400305>
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2022). *Organizational behavior* (18th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Ruggeri, K., Garcia-Garzon, E., Maguire, Á., Matz, S., & Huppert, F. A. (2020). Well-being is more than happiness and life satisfaction: A multidimensional analysis of 21 countries. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 18(1), 192. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-020-01423-y>
- Schnettler, B., Miranda-Zapata, E., Grunert, K. G., Lobos, G., Lapo, M., & Hueche, C. (2021). Testing the spillover-crossover model between work-life balance and satisfaction in different domains of life in dual-earner households. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 16(4), 1475–1501. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-020-09828-z>
- Sirgy, M. J., Kruger, P. S., Lee, D.-J., & Yu, G. B. (2011). How does a travel trip affect tourists' life satisfaction? *Journal of Travel Research*, 50(3), 261–275.
- Tamang, G. B. (2010). Antecedents and consequence of work-life balance. *PYC Nepal Journal of Management*, 3(1), 79–97.
- Unanue, W., Gómez, M. E., Cortez, D., Oyanedel, J. C., & Mendiburo-Seguel, A. (2017). Revisiting the link between job satisfaction and life satisfaction: The role of basic psychological needs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8(680). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00680>
- University of Minnesota. (1977). *Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire*. https://vpr.psych.umn.edu/sites/vpr.umn.edu/files/files/msq_booklet_short-form_1977.pdf
- VandenBos, G. R. (Ed.). (2015). *APA Dictionary of Psychology* (2nd ed.). American Psychological Association.
- Wright, S. L., & Perrone, K. M. (2010). An examination of the role of attachment and efficacy in life satisfaction. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 38(6), 796–823